

Application of LSB Based Steganographic Technique for 8-bit Color Images

Mamta Juneja, Parvinder S. Sandhu, and Ekta Walia

Abstract—Steganography is the process of hiding one file inside another such that others can neither identify the meaning of the embedded object, nor even recognize its existence. Current trends favor using digital image files as the cover file to hide another digital file that contains the secret message or information. One of the most common methods of implementation is Least Significant Bit Insertion, in which the least significant bit of every byte is altered to form the bit-string representing the embedded file. Altering the LSB will only cause minor changes in color, and thus is usually not noticeable to the human eye. While this technique works well for 24-bit color image files, steganography has not been as successful when using an 8-bit color image file, due to limitations in color variations and the use of a colormap. This paper presents the results of research investigating the combination of image compression and steganography. The technique developed starts with a 24-bit color bitmap file, then compresses the file by organizing and optimizing an 8-bit colormap. After the process of compression, a text message is hidden in the final, compressed image. Results indicate that the final technique has potential of being useful in the steganographic world.

Keywords—Compression, Colormap, Encryption, Steganography and LSB Insertion.

I. INTRODUCTION

STEGANOGRAPHY is an ancient technology that has applications even in today's modern society. A Greek word meaning "covered writing," steganography has taken many forms since its origin in ancient Greece. During the war between Sparta and Xerxes, Demeratus wanted to warn Sparta of Xerxes' pending invasion. To do this, he scraped the wax off one of the wooden tablets they used to send messages and carved a message on the underlying wood. Covering it with wax again, the tablet appeared to be unused and thereby slipped past the sentries' inspection. However, this would not be the last time steganography would be used in times of war.

In World War II, the Germans utilized this technology. Unlike the Greeks, these messages were not physically hidden; rather they used a method termed "null ciphering." Null ciphering is a process of encoding a message in plain

Mamta Juneja is working as Assistant Professor in Deptt. of Computer Science & Engg. Rayat & Bahra Institute of Engineering & Bio-Technology, Sahauran, Distt. Mohali (Punjab)-140104 India

Parvinder S. Sandhu is Professor with Computer Science & Engineering Department, Rayat & Bahra Institute of Engineering & Bio-Technology, Sahauran, Distt. Mohali (Punjab)-140104 India.

Ekta Walia is working with Department of Computer Science & Engg., Punjabi University, Patiala (Punjab), India.

sight. For example, the second letter of each word in an innocent message could be extracted to reveal a hidden message.

Although its roots lay in ancient Greece, steganography has continually been used with great success throughout history. Today steganography is being incorporated into digital technology. The techniques have been used to create the watermarks that are in our nation's currency, as well as encode music information in the ever-popular mp3 music file. Copyrights can be included in files, and fingerprints can be used to identify the people who break copyright agreements [5], [6], [8]. However, this technology is not always used for good intentions; terrorists and criminals can also use it to convey information. According to various officials and experts, terrorist groups are "hiding maps and photographs of terrorist targets and posting instructions for terrorist activities on sports chat rooms, pornographic bulletin boards, and other Web sites"[1].

This aspect of steganography is what sparked the research into this vast field[3] and [4]. Education and understanding are the first steps toward security. Thus, it is important to study steganography in order to allow innocent messages to be placed in digital media as well as intercept abuse of this technology[7].

II. LEAST SIGNIFICANT BIT INSERTION

One of the most common techniques used in steganography today is called least significant bit (LSB) insertion. This method is exactly what it sounds like; the least significant bits of the cover-image are altered so that they form the embedded information. The following example shows how the letter A can be hidden in the first eight bytes of three pixels in a 24-bit image.

Pixels: (00100111 11101001 11001000)
(00100111 11001000 11101001)
(11001000 00100111 11101001)

A: 01000001

Result: (00100110 11101001 11001000)
(00100110 11001000 11101000)
(11001000 00100111 11101001)

The three underlined bits are the only three bits that were actually altered. LSB insertion requires on average that only

half the bits in an image be changed. Since the 8-bit letter A only requires eight bytes to hide it in, the ninth byte of the three pixels can be used to begin hiding the next character of the hidden message.

A slight variation of this technique allows for embedding the message in two or more of the least significant bits per byte. This increases the hidden information capacity of the cover-object, but the cover-object is degraded more, and therefore it is more detectable. Other variations on this technique include ensuring that statistical changes in the image do not occur. Some intelligent software also checks for areas that are made up of one solid color. Changes in these pixels are then avoided because slight changes would cause noticeable variations in the area [9] and [10].

While LSB insertion is easy to implement, it is also easily attacked. Slight modifications in the color palette and simple image manipulations will destroy the entire hidden message. Some examples of these simple image manipulations include image resizing and cropping [11] and [12].

III. PROPOSED TECHNIQUE

After reviewing the current products on the market for steganography, it was determined that there was not a practical implementation for 8-bit images. Although network speed is increasing, and bandwidth problems are decreasing, file size is still of utmost importance and smaller file sizes are optimal in network communication. Thus, the current steganographic use of 24-bit images leads to slower communication and development of an 8-bit image format would be beneficial.

The aim of this research is to create a practical steganographic implementation for 8-bit images. A 24-bit bitmap image would be converted to an 8-bit bitmap image while simultaneously encoding the desired hidden information. An algorithm would be created to select representative colors out of the 24-bit image to create the palette for the 8-bit image. This palette would then be optimized to an 8-bit colormap that could be applied with minimal changes to the quality of the original image.

This process of compressing the image from a 24-bit bitmap to an 8-bit bitmap resulted in minor variations in the image, which are barely noticeable to the human eye. However, these slight variations aid in hiding the data. Since there would not be an original 8-bit image to compare with the stego-image, it would be impossible to discern that the slight variations caused by hiding the data are different from the slight variations caused by compression.

A practical steganographic implementation for 8-bit images enabled smaller file sizes to be utilized in steganographic communications. While also limiting the size of the hidden file, this implementation addressed issues that have been passed by in other applications, and provided a more compact vehicle for those secret communications that do not require a large cover-file.

IV. CREATING THE COLORMAP

The colormap in an 8-bit color image has a maximum of 256, 24-bit colors. However, in order to minimize the noise added when the least significant bits are changed, a starting colormap of only 240 colors is created. Sixteen additional colors will be added to the colormap by the time the final picture is written.

In order to select the 240 original colors, the image is divided into a grid of fifteen quadrants by sixteen quadrants, as seen in Fig. 1. One color is chosen from each of these quadrants by randomly selecting a set of X and Y coordinates within each quadrant. Calculations are then made to determine the index of the pixel in the array of RGBQUADS that represent the image data. (An RGBQUAD is a structure containing four bytes, one each for the red, green, and blue intensity and a reserved byte.)

Fig. 1 Image Overlaid with 15 X 16 grid

Each time a color is selected from a quadrant, it is compared to every other color in the colormap, and the minimum error between any two colors is calculated. If this error is lower than a certain error level (currently set at 20), then the new color is discarded and another color is selected from the image. After five attempts to find a color from a certain quadrant that differs enough from all the other colors in the colormap, the selected color is added to the colormap and the program moves to the next quadrant.

V. OPTIMIZING THE COLORMAP

The initial colormap contains 240 colors that were picked out of the original image. These colors were chosen from the entire image but that does not guarantee that these colors are the most representative of the colors that exist in the image. Therefore, the colormap must then be optimized to provide the best 240 colors for the colors in this particular image.

The optimization algorithm uses a Linde-Buzo-Gray methodology [2]. A pixel is chosen from the original 24-bit image and its RGB values are compared to the RGB values of every color in the colormap. For each comparison an error level is calculated using the mean absolute error of the red, green, and blue component of the color. The colormap color

that produces the smallest amount of error is the colormap color that is closest to the pixel's RGB values. The RGB values of the pixel are then added to the RGB values of the colormap color. A counter is implemented to keep track of how many pixels are assigned to each colormap color and is incremented each time a match is found. Approximately 25% of the pixels in the original image are run through this process. Once the algorithm has gone through the whole image, the RGB values of each colormap container are averaged by dividing the red, green, and blue values by the counter for that particular container. This process produces a colormap with slightly new, "better" colors in it. The process is repeated until the new colormap is considered to be optimized. To determine when the colormap is optimized, the error levels are recorded during each run and when a certain error level is attained the algorithm is finished.

VI. SORTING THE COLORMAP

Each pixel in an 8-bit color image is an 8-bit pointer to a 24-bit color in the colormap. Looking ahead to the LSB insertion, a pixel pointing to a red color could suddenly point to a yellow color by a simple flip of the least significant bit. In order to reduce dramatic noise such as that, the colormap was sorted so that similar colors are next to each other before the pixels are assigned to colormap colors. The sorting algorithm works as follows.

Beginning with the first color in the colormap array, the pixel that is the closest in color to the starting pixel is found using the mean absolute error measure. If the best match to a color results in an error level greater than 100 (meaning that there really was not a very good match to the color), a new color is created in the first open slot (using the sixteen extra spaces in the colormap) and this new color is used as the pair. The best-matched color is then switched with the color immediately following the starting color. The same procedure is repeated with the next color that has not been matched. Once the original 240 colors have been matched, additional colors are created to fill any of the extra sixteen positions left in the original colormap.

VII. ASSIGNING PIXELS

After sorting the colormap, the 8-bit image is almost ready to be created. An 8-bit bitmap contains a colormap of 256 colors and contains an assignment of each pixel to a color in the colormap. To assign the pixels to a colormap color, the original 24-bit image pixels are used. A pixel is chosen from the original 24-bit image and its RGB values are compared to the RGB values of every color in the colormap. For each comparison an error level is calculated using the mean absolute error of the red, green, and blue color components. The colormap color that produces the smallest amount of error is the colormap color that gets assigned to this pixel.

VIII. ENCODING THE DATA

The image is now ready to have data embedded into it. The encode function takes three parameters and two steps in order to complete. The data string of text, picture data, and binary data string are the three parameters for the first step in encoding the text into the image. The first step in the encoding function is to convert the ASCII text into its binary equivalent. In order to do this, each character of the text message is converted to its ordinal number (example: 'a' = 97). The ordinal number is then converted to binary using the following method called the division-remainder routine. An ordinal number is divided by two using the mod() function. This function returns either a one or a zero, which is then placed in a remainder array. This is continued until the dividend is zero. The ones and zeros in the remainder array is the binary equivalent of the ASCII ordinal number. Then, once all characters have been converted in this fashion, the binary data is embedded in the image by sequentially altering the least significant bit of the image data as necessary.

IX. CONCLUSION

This paper describes a technique to successfully embed data in an 8-bit color image. Additional features that could be added to this project include support for file types other than bitmap, and implementation of other steganographic methods. However, this research work and software package provide a good starting point for anyone interested in learning about steganography.

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